

Graphical Abstract

A: We analyzed a total of 2,006 complete genomes (>26 kbp) of *Coronavirinae* viruses (630 *Alphacoronavirus*, 1,099 *Betacoronavirus*, 12 *Deltacoronavirus*, and 265 *Gammacoronavirus*). We annotated four partitions (polyprotein ORF1ab, spike glycoprotein S, E protein, membrane protein M, and nucleoprotein N) by filtering and expanding BLAST results with a homemade Python package (parseOutfmt6). **B:** The strict consensus of the best heuristic results from parsimony analysis was mostly congruent with the maximum likelihood tree. We recovered the monophyly of all genera. We optimized host transformations (ten orders; we separated humans from other Primates) and found evidence supporting the hypotheses that viruses from bats were responsible for the human infections related to SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2, and MERS-CoV. **C:** The data plots show the minimum and the maximum number of host shifts on the clade of SARS- and MERS-related coronaviruses, including SARS-CoV-2. The number of shifts from Artiodactyla to humans is mostly inflated in the MERS-related clade after an ancestral virus from Chiroptera infected humans and Artiodactyla. Host shifts from Chiroptera to humans occurred three times on this clade, with humans infecting Carnivora hosts at least five times and humans infecting camels at least nine times. Shifts from Chiroptera to Eulipotyphla or from Chiroptera to Pholidota occurred only once in events that are not associated with human infections. **D:** Independent analysis of SARS-CoV-2-related clade. The figure shows that the infection of Pholidota from a Chiroptera ancestral is independent of the human infection by SARS-CoV-2. The 170 unique sequences from SARS-CoV-2 (out of 341 complete genomes), although not identical to each other, do not contain phylogenetically informative mutations. The lack of informative sites results in a large polytomy in which only two sequences from patients from Finland appear to be consistently nested together.